

TRAININGS FOR EDUCATORS AND PARENTS ON DEVELOPING DIGITAL CULTURE IN CHILDREN

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***Abstract.** The article discusses the importance of interaction between families and preschool educational institutions in developing a culture of competent use of digital tools, and substantiates the need to improve the level of digital literacy of educators and parents in the modern digital era. The article considers pedagogical foundations, teaching technologies, and effective methods for developing digital culture in children.*

***Keywords:** digital literacy, digital culture, educator, parent, learning, children, media education.*

Introduction. It is worth emphasizing that the rapid development of information and communication technologies deeply penetrates all aspects of modern society, including the early stages of education and upbringing. Children become familiar with digital devices from an early age, which affects their worldview, social adaptation, and moral values. Therefore, the formation of digital literacy and the development of digital culture in children is becoming an urgent task for educators and parents.

1. The concept of digital literacy and its importance.

Attention should be drawn to the fact that digital literacy is the ability to consciously, safely, and purposefully use digital technologies to search, evaluate, create, and disseminate information. Digital literacy includes not only technical knowledge, but also information culture, ethical standards and rules of digital security. The lack of this knowledge among teachers and parents can become a factor that hinders the positive development of children in the digital environment.

2. The need to form a digital culture in children.

Digital culture is a concept that includes cultural, ethical and legal norms for the use of digital media. Formation of this culture in children from an early age:

- protection from harmful content;
- ethics of online communication;
- the ability to assess the reliability of information;
- plays an important role in the formation of healthy digital habits.

This requires the modernization of pedagogical approaches of teachers and parents.

3. Training teachers and parents in digital literacy.

It merits attention that to improve the level of digital literacy, it is necessary to develop special training programs for teachers and parents. Training can be conducted in the following areas:

- Fundamentals of digital security (passwords, personal data, etc.);
- Digital ethics and culture (behavior on the Internet, interaction in social networks);
- Skills for selecting and analyzing information;
- Selecting suitable digital content for children;

- Developing family digital rules.

It is advisable to use interactive methods in trainings (conversations, discussions, watching videos, practical tasks).

4. Practical recommendations

- Organizing seminars on digital literacy together with parents in each preschool educational institution;

- Developing methodological manuals "Digital Etiquette" for parents;

- Preparing methodological recommendations for teachers on the use of digital technologies for pedagogical purposes;

- Children are recommended safe, educational and interactive digital applications.

Below are examples of diagnostic testing methods to determine the level of digital literacy of parents and teachers, as well as methods for protecting children from information attacks.

A. Test "Evaluate your digital life" (diagnostic method)

Purpose: examples of diagnostic testing methods to determine the level of digital literacy of parents and teachers are provided.

- Do you change your password every month?
- Have you explained the rules of online safety to your child?
- Do you share your child's content on social networks?
- Do you limit your child's screen time?

Result: The literacy level is determined and discussed based on the scores obtained.

B. Game technique "Safe and dangerous" (differentiation exercise)

Purpose: An example of how to explain how to help a child choose digital content:

Method: Participants are provided with various screenshots (cartoons, video games, advertisements, online chat scenes).

They must categorize them into:

- ✓ Safe for children
- ✗ Unsuitable for children

Discussion: Why this content is safe or dangerous, what measures should parents take - collective analysis.

C. Writing "Family Digital Rules" (practical task)

Goal: Formation of family order and responsibility in the digital environment.

Method: Participants in small groups or pairs develop rules, for example:

- How many minutes of screen time per day?
- Where are digital devices stored?
- How do we approach online communication?

Result: The finished rules are written on the board in the form of a textbook, and each group justifies its opinion.

4. Role-playing game "Digital situations" (simulation)

Goal: To teach how to respond to digital problems.

Method: Participants are given the following situations:

📱 Situation 1: Your child receives a threatening message from an unknown number on their phone.

📱 Situation 2: Your child is secretly surfing the Internet at night.

📱 Situation 3: Your child has viewed inappropriate content on the Internet.

Task: Each participant takes on the role of a parent or guardian and demonstrates how they would react in this situation.

Analysis: Each role play is discussed and positive approaches are noted.

5. Exercise "Separation of information" (development of critical thinking)

Goal: To teach participants to recognize false, inaccurate and manipulative content.

Method:

The trainer demonstrates various online posts, excerpts from articles or news headlines.

For example:

- "Learn English in 5 minutes!"
- «Install this app and your phone will work 2 times faster!»
- «Phones harm children's brains — it's proven!»

Task: Participants must explain whether each piece of information is true or false.

Conclusion. It is crucial to underscore that the formation of digital culture in children is one of the priority tasks of modern pedagogy. The role of teachers and parents in this process is invaluable. With the growth of digital literacy, the attitude towards the digital environment in the child's life is also formed. Therefore, the systematic organization of digital literacy training and the creation of a positive digital environment for children is a requirement of the time.

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